

**THE EFFECT OF SEARCH ENGINE OPTIMIZATION (SEO) ON WEBSITE
USABILITY**

By

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ABSTRACT

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Nowadays Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is a very popular topic. Everybody is talking and writing about it, because SEO makes you able to make more money with your website, because you can try influence your website's search engine ranking with it. Another popular topic is usability of the websites. In this area I read a lot about how to organize the homepage of a website, because it's told to be the most important part of a website. This is told to be the storefront, what you see the first and this is the place where you make your first decisions about the website you visited.

In the past, you had to remember the website's address and type it in the browser. As there were more and more websites on the Internet, the search engines became more and more popular. As browsers became more and more advanced, users started to use them more and more often and whenever in the last years I examined website statistics, I saw, that search engines became one of the most important source of traffic for the websites I developed or administered.

Web browsers also recognized this trend and all the mayor browsers integrated search engines into their address bars, so users don't need to type a correct domain name in the browser any more, many times they type just search terms instead.

My assumption is that optimizing the search engine results will result in a better usability of the website and higher user satisfaction. In this dissertation I try to show and measure the relationship between search engine optimization and user satisfaction.

DECLARATION

I hereby certify that this dissertation constitutes my own product, that where the language of others is set forth, quotation marks so indicate, and that appropriate credit is given where I have used the language, ideas, expressions, or writings of another.

I declare that the dissertation describes original work that has not previously been presented for the award of any other degree of any institution.

Signed,

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Chapter 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope

This dissertation aimed to show the effect of Search Engine Optimization (SEO) on website usability. Some selected SEO techniques was used on *www.telefonok.hu* website and the change of the user satisfaction was measured. The scope didn't include finding the best SEO techniques and the topic was not SEO itself. The focus was on increasing user satisfaction.

1.2 Problem Statement

A lot of people wrote and talked about SEO in order to make the websites rank higher in the search engine result lists. It was possible to find academic and industrial sources giving advice about increasing the rank itself. There were also a lot of literature about the usability of the websites. Although the search engine result pages became one of the most important entry point for the websites and often a lot of time and money was spent on SEO, the usability viewpoint was not researched in detail.

1.3 Approach

The project was started with a survey measuring user satisfaction. After running the survey, the selected SEO techniques were applied to the *telefonok.hu* website in order to increase the usability of the website for the visitors arriving from the search engines. After the changes were made, the same survey was run again. Conclusion were made based on the analysis of the two survey results and the web analytics data.

1.4 Outcome

The scholarly contribution of this project consists of examples of affecting and improving the user satisfaction of the visitors arriving from the search engines. The change of the user satisfaction is also measured and the new look of the search results is clearly documented.

Chapter 2. BACKGROUND AND REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Related Work

Krug (2011) compares web pages to real world objects, like real stores and makes it obvious that the best design methods of the webpages are really similar to the already tested and working designs of the brick and mortar world. Conventional stores use signs which everybody easily recognize because it's a working and tested method of communications with the customers. He prefers simple and obvious solutions on webpages also instead of tricky fancy magic solutions. For example a link should look like a link and it should always behave as a link. In this project this concept will be used and applied for the search engine result pages (which Krug didn't write about). After completing the project, the visitors in the search engines will be able to predict what kind of page they will see after clicking on the link in the search engine result link. It will be a like a traffic sign or shop sign for them. This way the telefonok.hu website will be more usable even before the visitors enter the site.

Ates (2012), Bohmann (2000) and Garrett (2002) write about how to design a good URL. Many of their suggestions are common. They all prefer simple and human readable URLs instead of using query strings and parameters, which is an easy to choose solution when we are working with dynamic web programming languages. The URL should be a very short description of the content it points to. Ates (2012) writes that in case we present an URL as a hierarchy, the upper levels in the hierarchy should also work. For example in case of a domain.com/products/product_name/ URL, domain.com/products/ should give us a list of products. Bohmann (2000) also emphasizes the importance of the obviousness. For example the format domain.com/products/product_name/ makes the user think that replacing the product name with another product name will result in a page which shows the other product. This project will eliminate the query strings in URLs in the telefonok.hu portal. All URLs will be short and meaningful. The hierarchical URLs' every level will be meaningful and working URL. Patton (2007) and Nielsen (1999) both agree that a well-designed URL improves the website's usability. Nielsen (1999) also wrote that

their research showed that the URL is especially important for the users when they want to assess the credibility of the destination. He even found that a well-designed, nice URL will increase the ratio of the searchers who click on the website's link in the search engine result list. He predicted that domain names will be less important and search engines will be more important because users will search instead of typing the domain names. And time showed that he was right according to his article.

Another improvement which will be done in this project is the usage of the Rich snippets. Those are special mark-ups, recognized by all the mayor search engines. Using those mark-ups will help the search engines recognize the content of the target page and improve the display in the search result lists. Goel, Guha and Hansson (2009) write about rich snippets. They write, that it's not guaranteed that the used mark-up will be parsed and / or displayed by the search engines, but they improve the chance of nice, readable, more usable search engine results. Elite-strategies.com (2012) also wrote that usage of Rich Snippets will increase website usability and present the content for the visitors even before entering the page.

My assumption is that since users tend to search for information instead of typing domain names directly in the browser, it's important to show already in the search engines' listings, that this site is a usable and credible website. Based on my research, nice and well-designed URLs and usage of Rich Snippets will help the users to decide if it worth clicking on the link or not, even before entering the website itself and this increase the usability of the website for them. My project will try to prove this assumption.

2.2 Literature

2.3 Industry Sources

Chapter 3. THEORY

3.1 Search Engine Optimization

3.2 Definition

Search Engine Optimization (SEO):

SEO is about increasing the rank of a given URL in a search engine. While there are more search engines, still the far most popular is Google and it delivers the most traffic. SEO usually means optimizing for Google and in this document it was used in this meaning. Many times though other search engines try to behave similarly to each other. For example Rich Snippets and sitemaps are used by more search engines.

Search engine result (result):

A result is the small excerpt of the web page, which is displayed on the search engine's search result list after executing a search query. Google (2012a) described the result page and the result itself in detail. The result list consists of a list of search results.

Figure 1. A typical search result in Google

The result consists of easily identifiable parts:

Title: On the picture the “Google” word in blue. It is usually the title tag of the referenced webpage. Visitors must click on the title to reach this webpage. Obviously this is the most important part of the result. This is the biggest, it's displayed with a different color and this is the element on the screen which the user has to interact with.

URL: in green on the picture. The full URL of the referenced webpage. Here a remark has to be made, that since the URL itself is displayed in the result list, the visitor can see it. It can influence their decision about which result to click!

Snippet: the rest of the displayed result. Often the meta description tag is used, but Google may choose anything else from the page if it fits the search query better.

Sitemaps: Sitemaps list all or some of the urls from the website. There are sitemaps for the visitors, but in SEO sitemap is the one generated for the search engines. As Google (2012b) wrote: " Google doesn't guarantee that we'll crawl or index all of your URLs. However, we use the data in your Sitemap to learn about your site's structure, which will allow us to improve our crawler schedule and do a better job crawling your site in the future. In most cases, webmasters will benefit from Sitemap submission, and in no case will you be penalized for it."

3.3 Methods

Although the topic of this dissertation was not the classical SEO, the goal was not to bring the website to the first place, very similar methods were used to the classical SEO methods, that's why the introduction to the SEO methods was necessary here. Search

engines don't publish the methods they use for ranking the search results, so most methods are based on industry testing and experience. Since Google is the most important search engine nowadays, the following methods were extracted from Google's (2010) SEO documentation.

Choosing keywords: SEO optimizes websites t keywords. Since most websites consists of thousands of words, it is not possible to make a website perform well in case of search on any selected words from the website.

Creating good titles: in SEO the titles are very important. Usually it is advised to include the keywords in the title. Titles are displayed in the search result list, too. Each page should have different title.

Marking important keywords: It advised to mark the important keywords with proper HTML markup. Many sources suggest heading tags, for example H1.

Usage of description tag: unless Google can find an even better matching part of the page, it displays the meta description tag in the search results. It's clearly stated by Google: "We frequently prefer to display meta descriptions of pages (when available) because it gives users a clear idea of the URL's content."

Illegal SEO techniques: According to NYC Web Design (2012) Page jacking, creating link farms, stuffing keywords, doorway pages and veiled text are illegal SEO techniques. Similar techniques must be avoided. Using illegal SEO techniques can easily result in being blocked from Google.

No AJAX: Although there are some special cases, AJAX is not really supported by the search engines. It's easy to see that AJAX is a word for a technology and the implementation can be so much different from each other, that it's really hard to process AJAX by the search engines. There are some suggestions and formats that are indexable, but they are not generally used and accepted.

3.4 Usability

3.5 Definition

There are a lot of different definitions of Usability or a Usable website. For me the most precise one was the one Krug (2011) gave: "It's not "Nothing important should ever be more than two clicks away." or "Speak the user's language," or even "Be consistent" It's... **"Don't make me think!"** (...) If you have room in your head for only one usability rule, make this the one." For me all the other good definitions were just variations of this one usually with lot more words.

Although it was not possible to think about usability as a theory related to websites only. As Krug also based on his statements and explanations on offline, real world objects, it was important to see that usability is a general theory. People always first experienced real world objects in their life before using on-line resources. Typography was also developed when there were no websites in the world. People read books first in their life and they use websites after seeing books.

3.6 Usability in Search Engine Optimization

3.7 Definition

It wasn't a well researched subject, so it was difficult to find any definition. Even Nielsen (2012) wrote only about the relationship between usability and SEO. He wrote: "Basically, SEO happens before the first click, and usability takes over from there. Both need to be good for a website to succeed. Having great SEO but lousy usability means that you'll get lots of traffic, but the visitors won't turn into customers. Conversely, a site with great usability but lousy SEO simply won't get many visitors, so it doesn't really matter how good it is."

Actually it was a must to argue with him. When he wrote "SEO happens before the first click" it must be a misinterpretation of the word SEO. Amongst the various SEO methods, only one, the link building happened before the the first click and according to Google (2012c), many of the link building methods were illegal and had negative impact on the website's performance. Since majority of the legal SEO methods were executed within the website itself and they affected mostly elements visible by the users, SEO and usability had a real close relationship. Keywords were visible on the pages, titles, heading tags, links were also. In case any site would hide them, that would be considered illegal by the search engines.

Many web usability sources - including Krug (2011) – used real world examples. using a real world analogy, the question was: would the stopping signs right in front of a shop be completely independent from the shop portals when usability matters were investigated? Could a customer find a real world food store usable if the stopping sign looked like a pub's?

Krug (2011) wrote "Like the cover of a magazine, the Home page needs to entice me with hints of the 'good stuff' inside" while Nielsen (1999) wrote "it is now much more common for users to type a company name, a site name, or even a domain name into a search engine than it is for them to guess the URL." So it became more common that the users' first met the websites in the search engine result list. What in the past was the Home page's role only – enticing the user with hints of the good stuff – it partially became the role of the search result in the search engines' result lists.

3.8 Methods

Chapter 4. ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

4.1 Preface

This project was a redesign of an already operating website, with a lot of existing data and algorithms already in place. It was not about creating the website from the scratch, it was a redesign of parts of the portal. The changes mainly affected the UI and the URLs. The topic of this DS was related to the URLs, so here only the related algorithm and content changes were designed using an ad-hoc design and described the anticipated UI changes.

The proposed changes were the following:

Changing the URL structure:

- to keep the URLs as short and simple as it's possible
- to reflect the changed search behavior
- Creating a crawlable property map from the phone parameters, thus multiplying the crawlable pages

Changing the page mark-up code:

- To use Rich snippets which make the site's content more visible in search engines' result list
- To simplify the structure and weight of the code

Changing general site behavior:

- To create intelligent 404 pages (avoid classical 404 messages, and present content instead of them)

- Anywhere Ajax is used on the site, it is used in search engine friendly way. The content became accessible without Javascript, too.

4.2 Analysis of the first survey

This project was started with a survey that was displayed for the visitors of the website and sent to some IT experts. After considering some possible tools, SurveyMonkey.com was chosen for hosting the starting and ending survey. Since the free functionalities were not enough, a monthly subscription plan was chosen.

The questions were the following:

- 1.) Your sex
- 2.) Your age is
- 3.) Your computer literacy skill level is
- 4.) The time you spend online weekly is
- 5.) How often do you visit this website?
- 6.) How do you rate this webpage generally?
- 7.) Where did you arrive from?
- 8.) The information you were looking for
- 9.) The website

Question 1-4 were collecting demographical information about the website's visitors. Question 5-9 were collecting usability related information from the participants.

As it was expected from a technology related website, majority, 66.7% of the visitors were male. Investigating the age of the visitors, it's quite interesting that the majority of the visitors were in the grown-up, money making age which could be an important information for the advertisers, too. The computer literacy skill was also expected to be average or above average, so it was not a surprise that 90.9% of the visitors had at least average skill level. 90.5% of the visitors spent more than 8 hours every week browsing the Internet. 57.1% of the participants visited the website the first time when they answered the survey.

Their general opinion was that the website is average (47.6%) or below average.

4.3 Pattern

Architecturally, the biggest change will be that the way of processing of incoming requests to apply the front controller pattern. In the current architecture, all request types have separate controllers (and the business logic is often mixed with the User Interface elements), as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Workflow of the requests before the redesign

The new architecture will be based on a Front Controller design pattern, which will greatly simplify the code (as presented in Figure 2). Using the Front controller pattern is a common and comfortable way of handling search engine friendly URLs.

Figure 3. Workflow of the requests after the redesign

4.4 Page and content types

The changes on the website affect the following content types:

- Telephones (mainly mobile phones). This is the main content of the website.
- Phone manufacturers
- News about telephones
- Deals
- Probably all the other contents from the current site will be removed.

There will be one dominant content type on each page types with excerpts and links to other types of content. For example on a phone page, there may be leads and links to news, too. The optimization will be done considering the dominant content type on the page only.

4.5 Format of the links and content of the pages

Telephones

Link format: telefonok.hu/manufacturer_model/

Example: telefonok.hu/nokia_e52/

The manufacturer and the model together define the phone to be displayed exactly.

The content will be a list of the properties of the phone, pictures, manual(s) and later prices uploaded by partners.

Phone manufacturer

Link format: telefonok.hu/manufacturer/

Example: telefonok.hu/nokia/

The name of the manufacturer determines the manufacturer exactly.

News about telephones

Link format: telefonok.hu/newsID-title_of_the_news_article /

Example: telefonok.hu/1232-a_new_phone_technology_was_invented/

The title of the article should be displayed in the link to make it SE friendly, but the title doesn't determine exactly the article, because it is possible to have two articles with the same title. That's why the id of the article is included in the link.

Deals

Link format: telefonok.hu/akcio/title_of_the_deal-dealID/

Example: telefonokh.hu/akcio/iphone_for_just_1_forint-1324/

"Akcio" in Hungarian means deal.

The title of the deal should be displayed in the link to make it SE friendly, but the title doesn't determine exactly the deal, because it is possible to have two deals with the same title. That's why the id of the article is included in the link.

The word "Akcio" is included in the link because the industry experience shows that users tend to search for akcio + product name very often.

Format for the URLs in crawlable property map

Link format: telefonok.hu/property1/property2/property3/property4/ etc.

Example: telefonok.hu/operating-system/screen-size/bluetooth/

4.6 Algorithm of the front controller

The flowchart of the Front Controller's basic logic is the following:

The order of the tests is determined by the time required for the tests. In the first version, caching of the URLs is not planned. Determining if the request was made for the index page takes constant time always, because it's a string comparison only. Determining if the request was made for an article or deal needs regexp matching on the URL and it's a bit longer.

Determining if the request was made for a manufacturer or phone requires a database query, so it is examined at the end.

A cache system was planned, where all the generatable URLs were cached where the key was the URL and the value was the data needed for processing and the type of request. It will result in a constant time required for recognizing any possible URLs.

4.7 Pre-processing URLs

Before entering the actual logic of the Front Controller, a pre-processing phase must be run. In the application, all URLs will be generated by a common algorithm using phone names, manufacturer names, news articles' titles and ids, and deals' titles and ids. Those elements can contain spaces, accents and special characters, which URLs cannot (apart from the non-standard behavior of some browsers). Some standard modifications must be made, for example all letters in the URLs must be transferred to small letters. For generating properly formatted, search engine friendly URLs, a unified algorithm will be used in case of all URL types.

So before processing the incoming URLs, the same algorithm's reverse version must be run. It's also a must to unify the ending of the URLs. URLs with an ending slash and without it are different from the viewpoint of a search engine, so to avoid punishment because of duplicate content, they need to be unified. The design decision is to use URLs with slash at the end. When an URL is entered without a slash at the end, without any

further processing, a 301 redirect (meaning that document was permanently moved) will be made. This processing can also be done in the webserver's configuration.

4.8 Using a framework

Using a framework simplifies many common tasks and lowers the time needed for development. In this project, the originally, the Symfony framework was planned to be used. After implementing some proof of concept route handlers, it was recognized, that this framework requires a really long learning period and while it is a well-designed framework, it would increase the complexity of the development needed. A decision was made to use another framework, called Fat-Free PHP Framework, which also implements the front controller pattern in a clean and effective way but doesn't require a long learning curve and it's possible to use the router component without having to use the full framework. This project aimed only a minor redesign, affecting mainly the routing and URL processing, so this framework seemed to be a good choice.

After developing the skeleton of the Front controller, it quickly became obvious that the Fat-Free php framework was not a good choice also. In case of the nice urls, the framework automatically removed the trailing slash, which made impossible to reach the target URL format.

At the end, a decision was made to develop a Front Controller manually, without using any frameworks.

Chapter 5. METHODS AND REALIZATION

5.1 Corrected errors

Before starting the project, the site was not updated regularly and was not really supervised. This resulted in a very buggy website. Although the full refactoring of the website was out of the scope of this Dissertation, it was not acceptable for me to leave the errors and not working functions untouched. The code was terribly unreadable and unstructured. The following changes were implemented which were not in scope of the Dissertation:

The unmaintained phone accessories were removed

The unmaintained java games were removed

The unmaintained operator logos were removed

The unmaintained ringtones were removed

The partner data upload function were removed

The not used and buggy integrated forum were removed

Since some of the functionalities are needed in the future, the preservation of the past's knowledge was important. It became a big refactoring, so it was not possible to work on it without a software versioning and revision control system. The selected system was Github.

The scope of the Dissertation was not the refactoring, so just the minimum required changes were made. In the code, the logic remained the existing one, but in case of many functionalities the business logic was organized into functions instead of unstructured monolithic series of orders. In most cases only equivalent transformations were made,

except some very important coding errors. Those were just two examples out of many similar:

Getting the most recent phone ID:

Originally this query was used in the code: "SELECT * FROM phones WHERE phone_id IN (SELECT MAX (phone_id) FROM phones WHERE permitted = 1)". This query was changed to the following: "SELECT * FROM phones WHERE phone_id = (SELECT MAX(phone_id) FROM phones WHERE permitted = 1)". This change resulted in a hundred times faster execution time. This function was one of the most commonly used db queries.

Querying the properties of a phone:

The original version's algorithm was the following: it queried all the possible properties in the database. After it in a foreach cycle in the php code run a separate query for all of the properties returning the value of the property related to the given phone. It means that querying the properties of a single phone required around three hundred database queries! It was replaced with a single query: "SELECT property_fields.*, property_values.property_value FROM property_fields INNER JOIN property_values ON (property_fields.property_id = property_values.property_id) WHERE (property_values.phone_id =\$phoneId) GROUP BY (property_fields.field_name)" It also resulted in a more than one hundred times faster execution time.

Although refactoring was not in the scope of the Dissertation, those it was simply impossible to leave those errors in the code. This means that a lot more time was spent on the development phase than it was planned.

5.2 Front Controller

After trying to use two frameworks, the decision was made to develop a completely customized solution for the given task. The goal was to change the routing of the telefonok.hu website without changing the functionality of the original webpage, and

without rewriting the old code (apart from the minimally necessary corrections and refactorings increasing only the readability of the code).

The original webpage didn't have any centralized routing functionality, so the first step was to direct all the traffic heading to the website – except the

```
RewriteEngine on
RewriteCond %{REQUEST_URI} (\.[a-zA-Z0-9]{1,5}|/)$
RewriteCond %{REQUEST_FILENAME} !-f
RewriteRule . index.php [L]

RewriteCond %{REQUEST_FILENAME} !-f
RewriteCond %{REQUEST_FILENAME} !-d
RewriteCond %{REQUEST_URI} !(\.[a-zA-Z0-9]{1,5}|/)$
RewriteRule (.*)$ http://telefonok.hu/$1/ [R=301,L]
```

requests for physically existing files, like images - to one file, the index.php. It was achieved using the apache webserver's .htaccess file. In the index.php the Route Interceptor was initialized and run.

Figure 5. The relevant part of the .htaccess file

5.2.1 RouteInterceptor class

The Route Interceptor class has only one public method, intercept(). This method contains the logic of the interceptor, all the others are supporting private methods.

All the desired URL formats are covered by route matchers. These route matchers examine if the entered URL matches a predefined route or not. Sometimes this matching is done by regular expression based text pattern matching, but in the case of phones and manufacturers, a database query is also needed. The first version of the RouteInterceptor's intercept method used the following algorithm:

```
if (route1Matched ()) {
    processRoute1 ();
} else if (route2Matched ()) {
    processRoute2 ();
} else if (route3Matched ()) {
    processRoute3 ();
} (...)

exit();
```

Functionally it was correct, but right after the first modification was needed, it was recognized that this structure is very hard to read and modify.

So a refactoring was done in order to increase the maintainability. During the refactoring the conditions were moved inside of the processRoute methods and all the processRoute methods were finished with exit;

After the refactoring, the intercept method looked the following way:

```
processRoute1();  
processRoute2();  
processRoute3();  
processRoute4();
```

This way the functionality remained the same, the efficiency of the code remained the same but the readability was increased and it became very easy to change the order of the processRoute methods.

The actual source code was listed in Appendix C.

5.2.2 Efficiency and complexity

Complexity:

According to McCabe, T.J. (1976) a cyclomatic complexity of an if else structure, when the structure is the following: IF (a) THEN b ELSE c, equals $C(a) * (C(b) + C(c))$

The first version of the method contained a chain of if else structures in case of a chain, the $C(c)$ itself equals $C(a') * (C(b') + C(c'))$. In case of a two level if then else structure, the complexity is:

$$C(a) * (C(b) + (C(a') * (C(b') + C(c')))) .$$

It equals:

$$C(a) * (C(b) + C(a') * C(b') + C(a') * C(c'))$$

at the end it is:

$$C(a) * C(b) + C(a) * C(a') * C(b') + C(a) * C(a') * C(c')$$

while after the refactoring, eliminating all the else parts in the new structure, the cyclomatic complexity is:

$$C(a) * (C(b) + C(a') * (C(b')))$$
 which simply equals:

$$C(a) * C(b) + C(a') * C(b')$$

That's why the new structure is easier to maintain, test and refactor.

Efficiency:

With the big O notation, the worst case execution time of an if else structure, when the structure is the following: IF (a) THEN b ELSE c is $O(a) + \text{MAX}(O(B), O(C))$.

Since it was a chained if-then-else structure, the worst case execution time was:

$$O(a) + (\text{MAX}(O(B), (O(a') + \text{MAX}(O(b'), O(c')))))$$

in the new structure, the worst case execution time became:

$$O(a) + O(a') + \text{MAX}(O(b), O(b'))$$

It's easy to see, that in case of both structures, the actual efficiency of the code depends on the order of the processing of different routes.

In the previous equations, $O(a)$ and $O(a')$ refers to the route matchers in the code. The route matchers execution time could be drastically different from each other. For example recognizing the index page of the website (accessing <http://telefonok.hu/>) required constant time, a simple string comparison. Recognizing a deal or a news article required regex pattern matching, which is slightly longer, but still a very quick process.

Recognizing a phone manufacturer or a phone required a database access, which was a time consuming process.

With the refactored structure it became easy to insert processing new routes or changing the processing order. It was also easy to run profilers or add loggers.

5.2.3 Route processors

Each route processor had the same general algorithm:

```
IF(urlMatcher) {  
  preprocessUrl();  
  SET globals;  
  executeRoute("oldPhp.php");  
  exit();  
}
```

urlMatcher was a function which could quickly decide if the URL was within the responsibility of the current Route processor or not. If it wasn't, the route processor simply existed, so the processing continues to the following route processor.

In case the URL matched the condition it preprocessed the URL. Preprocessing simply meant transforming the information in the URL to the data structure of the old application.

A remark must be made about using globals. In PHP, usage of global variables were not advised, it wasn't considered a good programming practice. Although the old application used this practice and without a more throughout refactoring of the whole application it wasn't possible to change to a better approach.

After setting the required global variables the the execute route method was called and at the end it exited the execution of the program.

Since all the route processors called exit() after calling the executeRoute() method, it could be logical to move it into the executeRoute() method. After careful consideration, the decision was made to call it separately, outside of the executeRoute() method, because it made the code more easy to read.

The executeRoute() method's basic functionality is very simple, it included the PHP file that was given as a parameter, so instead of creating a separate method, an

include(\$parameter) or require(\$parameter) could be enough. Externalizing this function made it possible to add some very usefull features to it.

executeRoute() handled the caching for the whole application. It wrapped all the old PHP files and cached the output. So the caching was added to all the content without modifying the old application's code. Apart from this function, executeRoute() was able to add logging and analytical functions which were removed from the current code, but it was the perfect location to add those supporting functions.

5.2.4 Caching

The pages mostly contained rarely changing information. Because of this reason the content of the pages could be easily cached. During the development a very simple, but still very efficient caching was developed. The cache keys were the urlencoded URLs, the cache content was the full, generated HTML output. The cached content was stored in files in a directory, the filename was the cache key.

This way the URLs, which were already in cache were served in a constant time so the response time became very low. According to some testers that were asked to test the webpage, it became much faster than it was before.

Speed was an important factor for search engines, they rank slow pages lower, so speeding up the website could be very important for any websites. Also in case a page was slower, probably more users left it unsatisfied.

5.3 Title

In the old application, all the pages had the same title. Although it was relatively well chosen, the visitors were not able to predict what would be the exact content of the specific page before clicking on the search result. It was changed during this project. All the pages got real, unique, descriptive titles.

The phone pages' title became the phone name itself.

The manufacturer pages' title became manufacturer name + "telefonok", for example: "Sony telefonok" which means Sony phones.

The page which lists the manufacturers had the title "Mobiltelefonok" which means Mobiles.

All the news article's title became the title of the news article itself.

The deals' title also became the title of the deal itself.

Since Google displays the title of the page as the title of the search result, choosing a proper title helped the users to identify what is expected after clicking on the search result.

5.4 Description

In the old application, all the pages had the same description, which was not a search-engine friendly behavior. Google, for example, used the description itself – or part of it – as the snippet in the search result, unless it found something more appropriate based on the actual user's search query. After the refactoring, the pages got a different, generated description. All of them became different. Although it still needed some refinement, fine tuning based on the analysis of the statistics and the visitors' behavior.

5.5 Rich Snippets

Snippet was the biggest part of the search result. Although, Google's first choice was the description, it tried to choose the most descriptive, the most relevant snippet to describe the result. That's why Google and other search engines started to accept Rich snippets which helped website owners and developers to describe what their content actually was. In the past search engines tried to figure out what to display and what not. What was the most appropriate, but short enough excerpt to display and describe? It was not an easy task for an algorithm. After introducing Rich Snippets, Website owners were able to explain to the search engines their content and so they were able to display more fancy search results which were more appropriate for the users.

During the current project, the following markups were added to telefonok.hu's pages:

Author markup: all the relevant pages got a link to the author's Google+ profile this way it became possible for Google to display the author's Google+ profile picture next to the search results.

Publisher markup: All the pages got a link to the Telefonok.hu's Google+ page using the publisher markup. It was also used by Google to display a profile picture next to the search results. Google, considering the popularity of the page, the relevancy to the search query and the number of +1s, can decide to display an excerpt and a link to the page's Google plus page, too, right next to the result list.

Product markup: All the phone pages became marked with the product markup. Although this would be more effective after the site will be extended to display offers from various sellers.

5.6 Sitemaps

In the old application there was a not regularly updated sitemap which was created with an unmaintained sitemap generator. Sitemaps are very important for search engines.

Google (2012b) wrote that they used the Sitemaps Protocol 0.9 This protocol was described in detail on sitemaps.org

Since this was an important functionality, which was missing from the application, a simple, easy to use, but effective sitemap generator was developed. The source code was listed in Appendix D.

A SitemapUrl class was created for representing a single URL and its parameters. The class was able to generate the representation of URL entry in the sitemap file in different formats.

The Sitemap class represented a collection of SitemapUrls. In my experience, websites usually consist of groups of pages sharing similar properties. When translated to the Sitemaps Protocol, it means that a website has many URLs sharing the same refresh frequency and the same importance. For example in the case of telefonok.hu the phones themselves were decided to be the most important. Then deals were a bit less important and so on. That's why the addListOfUrls method had the following signature:

```
addListOfUrls($urls, $priority = null, $lastModified = null, $changeFreq  
= null)
```

It accepted a list of strings – the URLs – together with the other parameters. This way it was possible to set the properties the properties of a lot of URLs in the same time.

At the end createSitemaps() method could be called and it automatically generated all the sitemap files. Sitemaps protocol accepts 50000 <url> tag resources within an <urlset> tag, that's why this method cut the output to multiple files if it was needed.

It was planned to publish the Sitemap Generator as an open source application after some generalization.

5.7 UrlGenerator

One of the important parts of this dissertation was the creation of nice, short and usable URLs. In the old application, URL generation many times was handled in different places of different independent PHP files and sometimes even in template files, which made it impossible to maintain and change the URL formats centrally. That's why it was very important to externalize this functionality to the UrlGenerator class, which can be easily extended, maintained, easy to read and understand. The source code was listed in Appendix E.

5.8 Auto Ajax Anchors

Using Ajax in web applications was a real challenge, because the modern internet applications used AJAX very intensively to make the websites more responsive, dynamic and easy to use. Analyzing the general behavior of the well-known web applications, it was recognized, that many of them, which used AJAX, used it in a very similar way. The behavior was simple: clicking on an element (most often an anchor element) resulted in a replaced or modified html tag without reloading the whole webpage. Obviously, replacing a small part of the webpage without loading all the images, javascripts, without re-rendering everything resulted in a much faster visible result for the user.

For the current project, the need was very similar, the only difference was that in that project, only the anchors were planned to be AJAXified. The reason was simple: the web search crawlers usually weren't able to process javascript calls, so the content accessed with the AJAX calls must have been accessible with standard, javascript-free navigation, also. In that case the users were able to see the pages very quickly and the crawlers still were able to crawl the website. It was also important to avoid serving different content for the search engines' crawlers than for the users which is an illegal behavior and can be punished by the search engines.

For that purpose a very small, but elegant solution was developed and was published to the open source community: a jQuery plugin, called Auto Ajax Anchors.

This plugin made it possible to attach a special simple click handler to any anchor elements using standard jQuery syntax. The click handler called a predefined server side script and provided this script with the clicked URL itself. In case there is no handler for the given URL in the server side script or in case of any errors during the processing, the original URL was loaded by the click handler, making the whole process safe and simple. In this project AJAX was used to replace specific parts of the HTML code – and this was the observed most common usage of AJAX calls, too – the other parameter accepted by the plugin was the selector of the html element(s) to inject the output of the server side processing.

It was possible to use any valid jQuery selectors both for selecting the anchors to ajaxify and for selecting the places of injection.

The source code was listed in Appendix F.

Chapter 6. RESULTS AND EVALUATION

6.1 A

6.2 B

6.3 C

Chapter 7. CONCLUSIONS

7.1 Lessons Learned

7.2 Future Activity

This topic was not researched yet in detail, so there is the possibility of further research of it. Since I'm studying Economy in a Hungarian university, the information technology aspects can be connected with sociological and economical aspects. It's an interesting possible research topic to investigate the effect of increasing the usability of the search engine results to the conversion rate and revenue in case of a e-commerce website.

7.3 Prospects for Further Work

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APPENDICES

Appendix A. STARTING SURVEY RESULTS

Telefonok.hu starting survey

Question 1: Your sex		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Female	33,3%	7
Male	66,7%	14
<i>answered question</i>		21
<i>skipped question</i>		1

Question 2: Your age is		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Below 18	9,1%	2
18-25	4,5%	1
25-35	27,3%	6
35-65	45,5%	10
Above 65	13,6%	3
<i>answered question</i>		22
<i>skipped question</i>		0

Question 3: Your computer literacy skill level is

Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Expert	22,7%	5
Above average	31,8%	7
Average	36,4%	8
Below average	4,5%	1
Low	4,5%	1
<i>answered question</i>		22
<i>skipped question</i>		0

Question 4: The time you spend online weekly is

Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Less then two hours	4,8%	1
2-4 hours	4,8%	1
8-16 hours	28,6%	6
More than 16 hours	61,9%	13
<i>answered question</i>		21
<i>skipped question</i>		1

Question 5: How often do you visit this website?

Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
This is the first time	57,1%	12
Daily	9,5%	2
Weekly	9,5%	2
Monthly	9,5%	2
More rarely	9,5%	2
I don't know	4,8%	1
<i>answered question</i>		21
<i>skipped question</i>		1

Question 6: How do you rate this webpage generally?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Extraordinary	0,0%	0
Above average	0,0%	0
Average	47,6%	10
Below average	23,8%	5
Very weak	9,5%	2
I don't know	19,0%	4
answered question		21
skipped question		1

Question 7: Where did you arrive from?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Google	33,3%	7
Bing	0,0%	0
Startlap.hu	9,5%	2

Other link from the internet	4,8%	1
I knew the URL	28,6%	6
Other	23,8%	5
answered question		21
skipped question		1

Question 8: The information you were looking for

Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
was on the first page	10,0%	2
wasn't on the first page, but it was easy to find	45,0%	9
was difficult to find	25,0%	5
was not found	20,0%	4
answered question		20
skipped question		2

Question 9: The website

Answer Options	I totally agree	I agree more or less	I don't agree	I don't know	R
contained the information I was looking for	3	12	3	3	
is easy to use	3	9	6	3	
structure is ordered logically	6	6	5	4	
is usefull and up-to date	2	6	9	4	
looks professional and authentic	4	7	5	4	
is modern and fresh	1	6	11	2	
					<i>answered question</i>
					<i>skipped question</i>

Appendix B. ENDING SURVEY RESULTS

Appendix C. SOURCE CODE OF THE ROUTE INTERCEPTOR

```
<?php
require_once 'commonFunctions.php';

/**
 * The class, handling the routing of URLs and caching
 */
class RouteInterceptor{
    /**
     * @var the internal variable for the called uri.
     */
    private $uri;
    /**
     * @var string the location of the cache
     */
    private $cachedir;
    /**
     * @var Turns on or off the simple cache
     */
    private $toCache = true;

    /**
     * The constructor sets the internal cache location and
the uri
     */
    function __construct(){

        $this->uri      = $_SERVER['REQUEST_URI'];
        $this->cachedir = PAGE_CACHE;
    }

    /**
     * The main cuncion.
     */
    public function intercept(){

        $this->processCached();

        $this->processUppercase();

        $this->processRoot();

        $this->processNews();

        $this->processOneNews();

        $this->processDeals();

        $this->processDeal();

        $this->processListOfManufacturers();

        $this->processManuals();

        $this->processManufacturer();

        $this->processOnePhone();
    }
}
```

```

        $this->processOther();
    }

    /**
     * In case no other handler was found
     */
    private function processOther() {
        $this->executeRoute("./old_index.php");
        exit;
    }

    /**
     * Processes list of manufacturer links
     */
    private function processListOfManufacturers() {
        if ($this->isListOfManufacturers()) {
            $this->executeRoute("manufacturers.php");
            exit;
        }
    }

    /**
     * Processes phone links
     */
    private function processOnePhone() {
        global $pid;

        $pid = $this->getPhoneIdIfValidPhone();
        if ($pid) {
            $this->executeRoute("phones.php");
            exit;
        }
    }

    /**
     * Processes one selected manufacturer
     */
    private function processManufacturer() {
        if ($this->isManufacturer()) {
            global $manufacturer;

            $manufacturer = str_replace("/", "", $this->uri);

            $this->executeRoute("phonesByManufacturer.php");

            exit;
        }
    }

    /**
     * Processes one deal
     */
    private function processDeal() {
        if ($this->isDeal()) {

            $parts = explode("/", $this->uri);

            $idArray = explode("-", $parts[2]);
            $lastPartId = count($idArray);

            global $nid;

```

```

        $nid = $idArray[$lastPartId - 1];
        $this->executeRoute("events.php");
        exit;
    }
}

/**
 * Processes list of news
 */
private function processNews() {
    if ($this->isNews()) {
        if (preg_match("|^/telefon-hirek/[0-9]+/$|",
$this->uri)) {
            global $lastNewsId;
            $tmp = explode("/", $this->uri);
            $lastNewsId = $tmp[2];
        }
        $this->executeRoute("news.php");
        exit;
    }
}

/**
 * processes user manuals
 */
private function processManuals() {
    if ($this->isManuals()) {

        $this->executeRoute("instructions.php");
        exit;
    }
}

/**
 * processes list of deals
 */
private function processDeals() {
    if ($this->isDeals()) {
        if (preg_match("|^/mobil-telefon-akciok/[0-
9]+/$|", $this->uri)) {
            global $lastNewsId;
            $tmp = explode("/", $this->uri);
            $lastNewsId = $tmp[2];
        }

        $this->executeRoute("events.php");
        exit;
    }
}

/**
 * processes one selected news
 */
private function processOneNews() {
    if ($this->isOneNews()) {

        $arrayOfParts = explode("-", $this->uri);

        global $nid;
        $nid = str_replace("/", "", $arrayOfParts[0]);
    }
}

```

```

        $this->executeRoute("news.php");
        exit;
    }
}

/**
 * processes the website root
 */
private function processRoot() {
    if ($this->isRoot()) {
        $this->executeRoute("./old_index.php");
        exit;
    }
}

/**
 * processes urls with at least one uppercase character in
it
 */
private function processUppercase() {
    if ($this->isUppercased()) {
        $target = "http://" . $_SERVER['SERVER_NAME'] .
strtolower($this->uri);
        header("Location: $target", TRUE, 301);
        exit;
    }
}

/**
 * If the url is already in cache, serve it.
 */
private function processCached() {
    if ($this->isValidInCache()) {
        print($this->getFromCache());
        exit;
    }
}

private function isUppercased() {
    return preg_match("[A-Z]", $this->uri);
}

private function isRoot() {
    return $this->uri == "/";
}

private function isOneNews() {
    return preg_match("^/[0-9]+-.[^/]+/$", $this->uri);
}

private function isNews() {
    return preg_match("^/telefon-hirek/$", $this->uri)
|| preg_match("^/telefon-hirek/[0-9]+/$", $this->uri);
}

private function isManuals() {

```

```

        return preg_match("|^/hasznalati-utmutatok/$|", $this->uri);
    }

    private function isDeal() {
        return preg_match("|^/akcio/.+-[0-9]+/$|", $this->uri);
    }

    private function isDeals() {
        return preg_match("|^/mobil-telefon-akciok/$|", $this->uri) || preg_match("|^/mobil-telefon-akciok/[0-9]+/$|", $this->uri);
    }

    private function isManufacturer() {
        global $db;

        $parameter = str_replace("/", "", $this->uri);
        return $db->db_is_manufacturer($parameter);
    }

    private function getPhoneIdIfValidPhone() {
        global $db;

        $candidate = str_replace("/", "", $this->uri);
        $parts      = explode("+", $candidate);
        if (count($parts) < 2) {
            return false;
        } else {
            $toTestManufacturer = $parts[0];
            unset($parts[0]);
            $toTestPhone = implode(" ", $parts);

            return $db->get_phone_id_if_valid($toTestManufacturer, $toTestPhone);
        }
    }

    private function isListOfManufacturers() {
        return $this->uri == "/mobil-telefonok/";
    }

    /**
     * Checks if the url is in cache and is valid
     * @return bool
     */
    private function isValidInCache() {
        //this just a very basic implementation currently

        if (!$this->toCache) {
            return false;
        }
        return file_exists($this->getCacheFile());
    }
}

```

```

/**
 * puts the url into the cache
 * @param $content
 */
private function putInCache($content) {
    //print(realpath($this->getCacheFile()));
    file_put_contents($this->getCacheFile(), $content);
}

/**
 * reads the url from the cache
 * @return string
 */
private function getFromCache() {
    return file_get_contents($this->getCacheFile());
}

/**
 * Wraps the old website's output with the cache handler
 * @param $fileToInclude
 */
private function executeRoute($fileToInclude) {

    if ($this->toCache) {
        ob_start("ob_gzhandler");
    }
    require_once($fileToInclude);
    if ($this->toCache) {
        $buffer = ob_get_flush();
        //print($buffer);
        $this->putInCache($buffer);
    }

}

/**
 * generates the cache file name
 * @return string
 */
private function getCacheFile(){
    //print("<!-- cachefile: ".realpath($this->cachedir .
rawurlencode($this->uri) . ".cache")."-->");
    return $this->cachedir . rawurlencode($this->uri) .
".cache";
}

}

```

Appendix D. SOURCE CODE OF THE SITEMAP GENERATOR

```
<?php
require_once ("SitemapConstants.php");
require_once ("SitemapUrl.php");
class Sitemap{
    private $sitemap;
    private $type;

    function __construct($type){
        if ($type != SitemapConstants::TYPE_TEXT && $type !=
SitemapConstants::TYPE_XML) {
            trigger_error(SitemapConstants::ERROR_UNDEFINED_TYPE,
E_USER_ERROR);
        } else {
            $this->type = $type;
        }
    }

    public function addListOfUrls($urls, $priority = null,
$lastModified = null, $changeFreq = null){

        foreach ($urls as $url) {
            $urlEntry = new SitemapUrl($url);

            switch ($this->type) {
                case SitemapConstants::TYPE_XML:
                    $this->sitemap[] .= $urlEntry->getXmlUrlEntry();
                    break;

                case SitemapConstants::TYPE_TEXT:
                    $this->sitemap[] .= $urlEntry-
>getPlainTextUrlEntry();
                    break;

            }
        }
    }

    public function createSitemaps(){
        $processingList = $this->sitemap;

        $fileContents = array_chunk($processingList,
SitemapConstants::SIZE_OF_ONE_SITEMAP);
        $fileId      = null;
        $filename     = "";
        foreach ($fileContents as $oneFile) {
            switch ($this->type) {
                case SitemapConstants::TYPE_TEXT:
                    $filename = "sitemap" . $fileId . ".txt";
                    $content  = implode("", $oneFile);
                    break;
                case SitemapConstants::TYPE_XML:
```

```

        $filename = "sitemap" . $fileId . ".xml";
        $content = SitemapConstants::XML_HEADER;
        $content .= implode("\n", $oneFile);
        $content .= SitemapConstants::XML_FOOTER;
        break;
    }
    $filename = "../..../.." . $filename;

    file_put_contents($filename, $content);
    $fileId = $fileId + 1;

    }

}

}

}
<?php
    require_once("SitemapConstants.php");

    class SitemapUrl{
        protected $loc;
        protected $lastModified;
        protected $changeFrequency;
        protected $priority = 0.5;

        function __construct($url){
            $this->loc = $url;
        }

        public function getXmlUrlEntry(){
            $urlEntry = "<url>\n";
            $urlEntry .= "<loc>" . $this->loc . "</loc>\n";
            $urlEntry .= "<priority>" . $this->priority .
"</priority>\n";
            if (isset($this->changeFrequency)) {
                $urlEntry .= "<changefreq>" . $this->changeFrequency .
"</changefreq>\n";
            }
            if (isset($this->lastModified)) {
                $urlEntry .= "<lastmod>" . $this->lastModified .
"</lastmod>\n";
            }

            $urlEntry .= "</url>\n";
            return $urlEntry;
        }

        public function getPlainTextUrlEntry(){
            $urlEntry = $this->loc . "\n";

            return $urlEntry;
        }

        public function setChangeFrequency($changeFrequency){
            $this->changeFrequency = $changeFrequency;
        }
    }

```

```

        public function setLastModified($lastModified){
            $this->lastModified = $lastModified;
        }

        public function setPriority($priority){
            $this->priority = $priority;
        }

    }
<?php
    class SitemapConstants{

        const TYPE_TEXT = "text";
        const TYPE_XML = "xml";

        const SIZE_OF_ONE_SITEMAP = 50000;

        const XML_HEADER = '<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<urlset xmlns="http://www.sitemaps.org/schemas/sitemap/0.9">
';

        const XML_FOOTER = '</urlset>';

        const ERROR_UNDEFINED_TYPE = "The selected type for the sitemap
is undefined";

    }

```

Appendix E. SOURCE CODE OF THE URL GENERATOR

```
<?php
class UrlGenerator{
    const BASE_URL = "http://telefonok.hu/";

    public static function getRootUrl(){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL;
    }

    public static function getDealsUrl(){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL . "mobil-telefon-akciok/";
    }

    public static function getNewsUrl(){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL . "telefon-hirek/";
    }

    public static function getInstructionsUrl(){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL . "hasznalati-utmutatok/";
    }

    public static function getManufacturersUrl(){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL . "mobil-telefonok/";
    }

    public static function getImpressumUrl(){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL . "impressum.php";
    }

    public static function getPricesUrl(){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL . "prices.php";
    }

    public static function getCopyrightUrl(){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL . "copyright.php";
    }

    public static function getManufacturerUrl($manufacturer){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL .
UrlGenerator::correctUrl($manufacturer) . "/";
    }

    public static function getPhoneUrl($manufacturer, $phone){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL .
UrlGenerator::correctUrl($manufacturer) . "+" .
UrlGenerator::correctUrl($phone) . "/";
    }

    public static function getNewsArticleUrl($id, $title){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL . $id . "-" .
UrlGenerator::correctUrl($title) . "/";
    }

    public static function getDealUrl($id, $title){
        return UrlGenerator::BASE_URL . "akcio/" .
UrlGenerator::correctUrl($title) . "-" . $id . "/";
    }
}
```

```
private static function correctUrl($url){
    $url    = iconv('UTF-8', 'ASCII//TRANSLIT//IGNORE', $url);
    $pairs  = array("/" => "+", " " => "+", ",", => "", "?" => "",
"." => "", "!" => "", "~" => "", "\"" => "", "!" => "");
    $result = mb_strtolower($url);
    $result = trim(strtr($result, $pairs));
    return $result;
}
}
```

Appendix F. SOURCE CODE OF AUTO AJAX ANCHORS

```
(function($) {
    var aaaHandler;
    var aaaTarget;
    $.fn.aaa = function(options) {
        if(options!=null && options.clickHandler!=null &&
options.clickHandler.length>0 && options.target!=null &&
options.target.length>0) {
            aaaHandler=options.clickHandler;
            aaaTarget=options.target;

            if( this.is("a")) {
                $(this).live("click",
                function (e) {
                    e.preventDefault();
                    var link=$(this).attr("href");
                    $.get(aaaHandler, {link: link}, function(data)
{
                            $(aaaTarget).html(data);
                        }).error(function() {
                            window.location=link;
                        });
                });
            }
        }
    };
})(jQuery);
```